

School-based citizen science: a current perspective and future outlook

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Abstract

School-based citizen science is increasingly recognised as a promising approach to enhance student engagement and connect science learning with meaningful, real-world contexts. This scoping review synthesises global school-based citizen science initiatives by analysing 300 peer-reviewed studies published in English up to April 2025. A systematic search was conducted across Scopus and Web of Science, focusing on projects implemented within primary and secondary school settings. The review aimed to examine the types of school-based citizen science projects, participation patterns, methodological approaches, and reported educational and scientific outcomes. As mapped to Australian Curriculum learning areas, Biology emerged as the most represented subject area, followed by Earth and Environmental Science and Digital Technologies, while Chemistry, Physics, Health and Physical Education, and Humanities and Social Sciences were less frequently represented. Geographic distribution revealed a strong imbalance, with Europe and North America accounting for most publications. Although a large proportion of studies reported scientific contributions, such as ecological and environmental data collection, far fewer detailed educational outcomes. Only a small subset of papers referenced conceptual or pedagogical frameworks for curriculum alignment. Only one publication reported the involvement of students and teachers as co-authors, demonstrating limited uptake of participatory research practices in dissemination. Integration of Indigenous Knowledges was rare, and participation models were predominantly contributory, with relatively few collaborative or co-created projects, reflecting patterns commonly reported across the broader citizen science literature. Nevertheless, the review identified a rapidly expanding and highly diverse body of school-based citizen science research, with many studies reporting authentic student engagement and meaningful connections between classroom learning and real-world contexts. These findings highlight both the field's growing scope and ongoing opportunities to strengthen participatory approaches and demographic representation.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the integration of citizen science within school settings has emerged as a dynamic and innovative approach to science education (Zoellick et al., 2012, Roche et al., 2020). This shift represents movement away from traditional forms of instruction, extending learning beyond textbooks and laboratory activities (Shah and Martinez, 2016). School-based citizen science embraces experiential, hands-on learning that supports scientific understanding while also fostering scientific stewardship and personal agency among students. Although numerous benefits for school-based citizen science have been identified, the global diversity of projects, methods, and outcomes has not yet been fully examined. Variability across geographic and curricular contexts suggests the need for a more comprehensive understanding of how citizen science is implemented in schools and how these implementations influence learning and scientific engagement.

This review provides an overview of the international literature on school-based citizen science. It examines the breadth of projects, their pedagogical contributions, the degree of student participation, and the implications for community involvement in scientific inquiry.

Integrating citizen science in schools

The incorporation of citizen science into school curricula responds to growing recognition that traditional instructional methods often fail to promote long-term understanding of scientific concepts (Shah and Martinez, 2016, Condon and Wichowsky, 2018). By involving students in authentic scientific investigations, schools offer transformative educational experiences that deepen conceptual learning and create meaningful connections with the local environment. Research conducted in the United States, Australia, Spain and Colombia (Paige et al., 2015, Condon and Wichowsky, 2018, Queiruga-Dios et al., 2020, González et al., 2022) illustrates the potential of this approach to promote critical thinking, problem solving, and personal engagement. Through participation in real scientific research, students can experience the relevance of science to their daily lives and contribute to broader scientific efforts.

A review of published school-based citizen science studies estimated that more than one thousand classrooms worldwide have implemented citizen science activities, with ecological observations and data collection representing the most common forms of participation (Pizzolato and Tsuji, 2022). However, this estimate reflects only initiatives documented in the published literature and is therefore unlikely to capture the full extent of classroom implementation. While these findings point to the promise of school-based citizen science, more research is needed to understand its uptake and long-term educational impacts.

Fostering Scientific Literacy and Stewardship

Beyond the classroom, school-based citizen science empowers students to assume active roles as informed and engaged citizens who advocate for meaningful change across multiple fields (Johnson et al., 2014, Eitzel et al., 2017). This educational model goes beyond knowledge acquisition and highlights the importance of applying scientific principles to real-world issues, including early warning systems for infectious diseases, climate change mitigation and species conservation (Newman et al., 2012, Meentemeyer et al., 2015, McKinley et al., 2017, Tal et al., 2023). As students investigate matters that directly affect their communities, they develop a deeper appreciation for the 'scientific method' and a heightened sense of civic responsibility (Johnson et al., 2014, Ballard et al., 2017). This dual focus on scientific literacy and civic engagement enriches the learning experience and lays the foundation for a population equipped to address local and global challenges (Schuttler et al., 2019, Roche et al., 2020, González et al., 2022).

Although citizen science has strong potential to support scientific literacy, its adoption in schools remains limited. A recent study of Australian teachers reported an impressive level of engagement, with 41% (n = 295) incorporating citizen science into their classrooms, most often through ecological monitoring activities. Teachers who had not yet implemented citizen science identified shared challenges, including limited time, lack of familiarity and uncertainty regarding curriculum alignment. Notably, 92% indicated they would be more likely to use citizen science if projects were clearly linked to curriculum requirements (Braz Sousa et al., 2024). These findings suggest that while interest and participation are growing, targeted support and clearer guidance remain essential for broader and more sustainable adoption.

From Past Reviews to New Perspectives

A recent systematic review of 49 peer-reviewed publications identified 46 citizen science initiatives implemented in primary and secondary school contexts (Solé et al., 2023). While most projects aimed to meet both scientific and educational objectives, student participation was typically limited to data collection, and only a minority engaged in deeper scientific practices such as data analysis or research design. Educational goals often focused on raising awareness, with fewer initiatives targeting inquiry skills, STEM identity, or understanding of the nature of science. Despite widespread implementation, the exact number of schools involved across studies was not consistently reported, highlighting a gap in the literature.

Similarly, Pizzolato and Tsuji (2022) conducted a systematic mapping of 77 peer-reviewed studies to

assess the scope and characteristics of citizen science initiatives in K–12 school-based learning environments. They found that 49 of the studies reported student participation, totalling 143,588 students, with 24 studies reporting involvement from 1,081 school classes. Most initiatives (87%) involved students in data collection, with ‘distributed intelligence’ being the most common participation level, where students carry out defined tasks in a project that remains scientist-led (Haklay, 2012). A smaller number of initiatives engaged students in roles with greater participation, with only four studies classified as ‘extreme citizen science’, where students co-designed and led the research process (Haklay, 2012). Across all projects, Ecology, Hydrology, and Public Health were the most common themes.

While these studies offer a valuable overview of project characteristics and levels of student participation, this review builds on and extends this work by providing an updated and more inclusive perspective. It incorporates a broader definition of citizen science; recognising multiple terms and approaches used across diverse countries and contexts, and explores not only how school-based citizen science has been implemented around the world, but also its educational impacts and the key factors needed to sustain and strengthen these initiatives.

Research Questions

This literature review explored the central research question: What is the current state of research on the implementation, outcomes, and future perspectives on school-based citizen science globally?

To address this, four specific research questions guided the analysis:

- 1) What types of school-based citizen science projects are being implemented internationally, and what is their disciplinary and methodological diversity?
- 2) Who participates in these initiatives, including consideration of age groups, demographics, regions and school contexts?
- 3) What educational and scientific outcomes are reported in the literature?
- 4) What conceptual or educational frameworks are used to guide school-based citizen science when reported?

METHODS

We employed a scoping review approach to examine the breadth and diversity of school-based citizen science research. For the purposes of this review, school-based citizen science was defined as citizen science projects implemented within primary or secondary school settings, where students participated in one or more stages of the research process as part of formal educational activities. This approach was selected because it enables comprehensive mapping of methodological practices,

project types and reported outcomes. The review followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta Analyses extension for scoping reviews (PRISMA ScR) (Tricco, 2018).

Search Strategy

We systematically searched the Scopus and Web of Science databases and included studies published in English up until April 2025. As citizen science is also sometimes referred to as community science or participatory science, we included all these terms in the search strategy.

The search terms encompassed a spectrum of keywords such as "school-based citizen science", "school" or "classroom" + "citizen science" or "community science" or "participatory science" (Table 1).

Table 1. Search strategy components, including keywords, language criteria, and databases used for the literature search.

Category	Keywords
Citizen science	Citizen science, community science, participatory science
School	School-based, school, classroom
Language	English
Database	Scopus, Web of Science

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Studies were included if they specifically examined citizen science initiatives integrated within school settings, while those focusing solely on non-school environments (including tertiary education settings) were excluded. We screened titles, abstracts and full texts to ensure alignment with the inclusion criteria, and reference lists of selected studies were manually reviewed to achieve comprehensive coverage. These methods were piloted in October 2023 to identify gaps and overlaps, refining the keywords used for a more relevant research inquiry.

For each source eligible for inclusion, the PEO (population, exposure, outcome) approach was used to specify populations (e.g., age group, region, geographic location and school years), exposure (i.e., the types of citizen science activities undertaken), and outcomes of the projects including both specific research objectives as well as general learning outcomes for students. The PEO framework provides a systematic and rigorous overview of the factors relevant in understanding the current state of research in school-based citizen science (Moola et al., 2015).

Screening Process

References were exported to EndNote 20 for the initial removal of duplicates and title/abstract screening. Suitable articles were exported to Covidence for full-text review. Data extraction was performed via Microsoft Excel using a template that included the following fields: Paper title, authors, year of publication, journal of publication, project region, targeted age group, project area, project outcomes, and citizen science category.

Learning Areas Represented and Project Typologies

To classify the subject areas represented in the projects, we referred to the Australian Curriculum learning areas (ACARA, 2020). The curriculum divides learning into several areas, including English, Mathematics, Science (Biology, Chemistry, Earth and Environmental Science, and Physics), Humanities and Social Sciences (Civics and Citizenship, Economics and Business, Geography and History), The Arts, Technologies (Design and Technologies and Digital Technologies), Health and Physical Education, and Languages. Project outcomes were classified based on the outcomes explicitly reported by authors in each publication and grouped as scientific or educational outcomes.

Citizen science project types were classified using the contributory, collaborative, and co-created model described by Bonney et al. (2009a). Where studies did not explicitly report their project classification, the model of engagement was determined based on the project descriptions provided in the manuscript.

Project Methods and Learning Outcomes

The methods used in the citizen science projects and reported learning outcomes were categorised through an iterative thematic coding process. To develop the coding framework, two authors independently reviewed and discussed the first 50 included studies in a pilot coding stage to identify the most frequently reported skills and competencies across the literature. Through this process, recurring categories were refined collaboratively and applied across the remaining studies.

Skills were coded based on the terminology and descriptions explicitly reported by the study authors. Common categories included technical or practical skills, observation skills, data collection, data entry, data analysis, science communication, inquiry skills, content knowledge, numeracy and literacy. Studies were assigned to multiple categories where appropriate. The coding system remained flexible throughout the review process, allowing additional categories to be incorporated where new themes were identified.

RESULTS

The database search identified 1,838 records. After duplicate removal in EndNote, 1,158 unique records were exported to Excel and screened for eligibility based on titles and abstracts. Of these, 638 records progressed to full-text review and were assessed in Covidence (Figure 1). Title and abstract screening (Phase 1) was conducted independently by two reviewers (LBS and TH), and full-text screening (Phase 2) was conducted independently by LBS and WZ. Following full-text assessment, 300 papers met the inclusion criteria and were included in the review, collectively describing 269 different school-based citizen science projects. The full list of included studies is presented in Supplementary Table 1 (Braz Sousa et al., 2026).

Figure 1. PRISMA extension for Scoping Reviews flow diagram showing the scoping review process for school-based citizen science projects available in the SCOPUS and Web of Science databases.

The number of publications on school-based citizen science has increased substantially over time, particularly since 2018. This growth is even more pronounced between 2020 and 2024, with annual publication numbers more than doubling, reaching their highest levels (over the period under review) in 2024 with 57 publications in a single year (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Number of publications on school-based citizen science projects published per year between 2001 and 2024.

Projects Distribution

Based on the distribution of studies identified, school-based citizen science projects were unevenly represented across global regions. Europe accounted for the largest number of publications ($n = 135$), followed by North America ($n = 78$), Oceania ($n = 25$) and Asia ($n = 25$). Fewer studies were reported in South America ($n = 14$), and representation was lowest in Africa ($n = 5$). Within North America, 65 of the 89 projects were conducted in the United States, indicating limited representation from other countries in the region, particularly those where Spanish and Indigenous languages are predominant. A similar pattern appeared in South America, where six of the 14 identified projects were based in Chile, often through collaborations with European partners, leaving fewer publications describing projects in neighbouring countries. In Oceania, 16 of the 25 studies originated in Australia, with limited representation from other nations (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Global distribution of school-based citizen science projects described in the literature (per continent). *Represents projects described in more than one continent.

School Type

Among studies reporting these data, school-based citizen science projects collectively reported engaging more than 261,600 students from 6,682 classrooms at 5,509 schools across 49 countries. Where school type was described (33% of studies), 40% of participating schools were public or government schools, 14% were private or other independent schools, including religious schools, 6% included mixed public and private settings, and 39% were described using other contextual categories such as rural, technical, agricultural, specialist or eco-schools (Figure 4). Where year levels were specified, 16% of projects took place in primary schools, 57% in secondary schools, and 16% involved multiple year groups spanning kindergarten to Year 12 (Figure 5). School year information was not reported in the remaining studies. The figures described in this paragraph represent minimum estimates, as studies did not consistently report participant numbers, school type, or school year(s).

Figure 4. Distribution of school types described in school-based citizen science projects included in the review.

Figure 5. Distribution of school year levels engaged in school-based citizen science projects included in the review.

Learning Areas Represented in School-Based Citizen Science Projects

The 300 included papers described projects across a wide range of learning areas, including English, Mathematics, Science, Humanities and Social Sciences, Arts, Technologies, Health and Physical Education, and Languages. Several projects were multidisciplinary and spanned multiple learning areas (Table 2).

Table 2. Main curriculum learning areas and subareas represented in school-based citizen science projects included in the review, classified according to the Australian Curriculum learning areas.

Science	224	Biology	102
		Chemistry	11
		Earth and Environmental Science	88
		Physics	21
Humanities and Social Science	23	HASS	10
		Civics and Citizenship	6
		Economics and Business	1

		Geography	4
		History	1
		Languages	1
Technologies	30	Design and Technologies	6
		Digital Technologies	24
Health and Physical Education	24	Health and Physical Education	24

Across the 300 school-based citizen science papers reviewed, Science was the most represented curriculum learning area, accounting for 224 projects (75%). Technologies received the next highest representation, (n = 30, 10%), followed by Health and Physical Education (n = 24, 8%) and Humanities and Social Science (n = 23, 8%) (Figure 6).

Within Science, Biology was the most frequently represented subarea (n = 102, 34%), with many projects focusing on biodiversity monitoring, species identification, and ecological data collection. These projects often involved monitoring biodiversity such as birds, rats, crabs, mosquitoes, soil organisms, and insects within school grounds (Hiller and Kitsantas, 2014, Wisittanawat et al., 2022, Aivelo, 2023, Kervinen and Aivelo, 2023, Craig et al., 2024). One example is the Australian Insect Investigators citizen science project, which contributed to the discovery, collection, and formal taxonomic description of seven new parasitoid wasp species. This included four species associated with regional South Australian schools (Fagan-Jeffries and Austin, 2021), and a further three species collected through collaborations with schools and communities in Queensland, New South Wales, and Western Australia (Slater-Baker et al., 2025).

Earth and Environmental Science was the second most represented Science subarea, encompassing 88 projects (29%). Many of these initiatives integrated interdisciplinary themes such as Agriculture, Ecology, Marine Science, Geology, Computer Science, and Public Health. Air quality monitoring emerged as a prominent focus, reported in 14 projects conducted across countries, including the United States, the United Kingdom, Denmark, and Spain. Examples included SAMHE (Chatzidiakou et al., 2023) and xAire (Perelló et al., 2021), in which students used monitoring instruments to measure classroom or school-ground concentrations of PM_{2.5}, CO₂, and NO₂ (Moore et al., 2020, Perelló et al., 2021, Catarino et al., 2023, Toftum and Clausen, 2023). Another recurring theme involved coastal

and marine litter surveys, also reported in 14 projects. Examples included COLLECT, implemented across Africa and Asia (Catarino et al., 2023), SEACleaner in Europe (Locritani et al., 2019), and the National Sampling of Small Plastic Debris program in Chile (Hidalgo-Ruz et al., 2018).

Figure 6. Subareas of school-based citizen science projects described in the literature per subject.

Physics was represented in 21 projects (7%), many of which involved students in large-scale astronomical investigations. One example was the EXTraS project, in which students contributed to the discovery of a flaring X-ray source in the globular cluster NGC 6540 (D'Agostino et al., 2020). Only 11 of the 300 articles (4%) were chemistry-related, and all were conducted in secondary schools. These projects explored topics such as calcium carbonate synthesis, water chemistry, and agricultural pollution, often linking chemical concepts with environmental and public health contexts (Abbott et al., 2018, Araújo et al., 2023, Murray et al., 2023). Another notable example is Breaking Good, an open-source drug discovery citizen science project where students synthesise potential medicines for the treatment of diseases with low market incentives, such as malaria and toxoplasmosis, while exploring issues related to medicine accessibility, ethics, equity, and public health (Golombic and Motion, 2021, Dalyot and Golombic, 2022).

A total of 24 projects (8%) were classified within Health and Physical Education, with most conducted in North America and Europe, together representing over 80% of the studies in this category. These projects commonly connected science learning with everyday health and community issues; engaging students in investigations related to topics such as healthy lifestyles, food choices, mental health, Lyme disease, asthma, and environmental health risks (Day and Fryxell,

2022, Gallagher-Mackay and Corso, 2023, Gell et al., 2023, Heinert et al., 2023, Wargers et al., 2023). Several initiatives also explored applied topics from public health and microbiology, including medical entomology, antimicrobial discovery, water quality and human health, and biofilm formation in household environments (Abe et al., 2016, Maicas et al., 2020, Perelló et al., 2021, Prunuske et al., 2021, Ushe et al., 2021).

A total of 23 projects were classified within the Humanities and Social Sciences learning area. These projects were implemented across Europe, South America, and Asia and involved students from preschool through to Year 12. Many explored language, communication, and cultural identity through participatory research approaches. For example, high school students in Hungary contributed to the creation of a dialect corpus by collecting, transcribing, and analysing recordings of the Palóc dialect within their communities (Szabó et al., 2025). Similarly, a co-created citizen science program in Poland engaged secondary school students in 18 projects investigating multilingualism, communication, language learning, and literacy practices relevant to their local contexts (Molek-Kozakowska and Laihonen, 2024).

Aims and methods of projects

School-based citizen science projects employ a wide range of methods to engage students in hands-on scientific research. Observational techniques were particularly common. Students used binoculars to track bird species, magnifying glasses to study insects or plants and simple sampling tools to collect water from rivers for ecosystem health analyses (Thornton and Leahy, 2012, Matthews et al., 2014, Mnisi et al., 2021). Other projects involved collecting and categorising natural materials such as shells or beach debris as part of environmental clean-up activities, enabling students to quantify pollutants and reflect on human impacts on ecosystems (Wichmann et al., 2022, Murray et al., 2023). Some studies also compared the effectiveness of different insect traps, providing opportunities for hypothesis testing, structured data collection and introductory experimental design (Saunders et al., 2018).

Beyond observational approaches, several projects incorporated experimental or creative components. For instance, students constructed devices such as marine pollution trackers to support environmental monitoring (Merlino et al., 2023a, Merlino et al., 2023b). Qualitative methods were also used, with students interviewing peers, parents or community members to gather insights into local biodiversity or environmental issues. These activities supported the development of skills in communication, reflection and data interpretation.

Reported outcomes

Of the 300 articles included in the review, 42% reported primarily educational outcomes, 26% reported primarily scientific outcomes, and 31% reported both educational and scientific outcomes. Many projects contributed directly to scientific efforts, including biodiversity data collection, improvements to seismological monitoring tools, and the identification of new chemical compounds for drug discovery (Dalyot and Golumbic, 2022, Kobayashi et al., 2023, Merlino et al., 2023b, Morton et al., 2023, Thiel et al., 2023). Educational outcomes commonly included gains in conceptual understanding, numeracy and literacy skills, increased confidence in scientific practices, and greater awareness of environmental and community issues (Rodríguez-Loinaz et al., 2022, Wisittanawat et al., 2022, Payne et al., 2023). Some studies also noted challenges related to sustaining student engagement and ensuring data accuracy (Molek-Kozakowska and Laihonon, 2024, Szabó et al., 2025).

Theoretical Frameworks

Most papers did not report the use of an explicit educational or theoretical framework to guide the adaptation or implementation of citizen science projects in school settings, with 262 studies (83%) providing no clear framework. Among the studies that did report a guiding framework, several drew on educational, social, or participatory theories to support project design and student engagement. Examples included Two-Eyed Seeing (Walker et al., 2023), the Ecological Framework of Child Development (Gallagher-Mackay and Corso, 2023), socio-ecological approaches (King et al., 2021), and the Theory of Planned Behaviour (Wargers et al., 2023). A smaller number of studies also referenced citizen science-specific frameworks, particularly the European Citizen Science Association's Ten Principles of Citizen Science (Walsh et al., 2024, West et al., 2023), which were used to guide project implementation and participation practices.

Engaging First Nations Knowledge and Remote School Communities

Despite the limited number of studies involving rural, regional or remote schools, two recent Australian examples demonstrate the potential of school-based citizen science to engage First Nations communities and contribute to scientific outcomes. In Quinkan Country, Cape York (Far North Queensland), Riley et al. (2025) report an arts-based digital literacy program where Aboriginal students used local rock art and community knowledge to create "pixel critters" for a machine-learning project cataloguing rock art motifs. The study documents increased student engagement and digital confidence, alongside noted challenges, including limited digital infrastructure and variable teacher support. Slater-Baker et al. (2025) present another example from regional schools, where students participating in the Insect Investigators project collected specimens that led to the

description of three new species of parasitoid wasps. Using DNA barcoding, morphological taxonomy and a co-naming process with students, the study shows that school-based citizen science can enable young people in remote communities to contribute directly to biodiversity discovery and documentation.

Engagement and Typologies

As described in the Methods section, not all papers explicitly classified the citizen science approach applied. Among those that did, contributory projects were most common, representing 211 studies (70%). These projects typically involved students primarily in data collection and submission activities. Collaborative approaches accounted for 56 studies (19%) and generally engaged students and teachers more actively in data analysis, interpretation, or decision-making alongside researchers. Co-created projects were the least represented, with only 33 studies (11%) describing initiatives in which students, teachers, or communities contributed to shaping research questions or methodological design, allowing for deeper engagement with the research process.

The terminology used to describe participatory approaches varied considerably across the literature, with many papers using multiple terms to characterise their projects. Consequently, the frequencies reported below are not mutually exclusive. The term citizen science was the most frequently used, appearing in 288 papers (96%). Other terms were reported less commonly, including community science (n = 18; 6%), participatory science (n = 12; 4%), crowdsourcing (n = 3; 1%), participatory research (n = 3; 1%), citizen inquiry (n = 2; 1%), community-based monitoring (n = 2; 1%), civic science (n = 2; 1%), and participatory action research (n = 2; 1%). Some studies also adopted other descriptors such as volunteer scientists, contributive approach, participatory methods, citizen social science, and citizen monitoring.

Discussion

This review has synthesised the global landscape of school-based citizen science and examined how such projects are distributed and implemented across educational contexts. Using the Australian Curriculum Standards to classify subject areas allowed us to identify the breadth of disciplinary engagement represented in the literature and to consider how citizen science is being used to support science education more broadly. The findings reinforce previous research showing that school-based citizen science is most commonly situated within Ecology, Biodiversity Monitoring and Environmental Stewardship activities (Pizzolato and Tsuji, 2022, Solé et al., 2023), reflecting broader trends within citizen science more generally, where environmental and ecological projects dominate participation and publication outputs (Bonney et al., 2009a, Pelacho et al., 2021). Several projects reviewed in this study engaged students in authentic scientific practices such as species

identification, environmental monitoring, data collection and interpretation, aligning with inquiry-based and place-based approaches to science education (Ballard et al., 2017, Roche et al., 2020).

The review also highlights the growing recognition of schools as important settings for participatory science and community engagement. Previous literature has suggested that citizen science can support not only scientific literacy, but also student agency, environmental stewardship and stronger connections between schools, communities and scientific institutions (Johnson et al., 2014, Schuttler et al., 2018). However, the findings of this review indicate that implementation remains uneven across disciplines, regions and participation models. While some projects moved towards collaborative or co-created approaches that positioned students as active contributors to scientific inquiry, most remained contributory in nature, with students primarily involved in data collection. This mirrors wider patterns identified across the citizen science literature, where deeper forms of participation and shared decision-making are less common despite increasing calls for more inclusive and participatory practices (Bonney et al., 2009b, Eitzel et al., 2017). Together, these findings suggest that school-based citizen science is an expanding and promising field, but one that still requires stronger theoretical grounding, broader disciplinary representation and more equitable global participation.

Project Distribution

The distribution of projects reveals a strong geographic imbalance, with most studies published in English originating from the United States and Europe. This pattern reflects broader trends in global scientific publishing and citizen science literature, where research outputs are often concentrated in the Global North (Pelacho et al., 2021). In contrast, countries in the Southern Hemisphere and the broader Global South were markedly underrepresented, despite their cultural, linguistic and ecological diversity and the significant potential for citizen science to support local educational and environmental priorities. The limited number of studies from Africa, South America and parts of Asia may reflect differences in reporting and publication practices rather than lower levels of implementation. Challenges related to research funding and infrastructure, including the predominance of English-language databases and publications, may contribute to the underrepresentation of initiatives from these regions. These disparities highlight the need for more inclusive global efforts to document and expand school-based citizen science initiatives, particularly in regions where such work may be occurring but remains inaccessible through English-language literature.

Learning Outcomes

Among the studies that reported educational outcomes, common benefits included the

development of technical and practical skills such as observation, species identification, environmental monitoring, data collection, data entry and data analysis. Some projects also reported gains in communication skills, inquiry processes, scientific literacy and confidence in engaging with scientific practices. These findings align with the broader citizen science literature suggesting that authentic participation in research can strengthen student engagement and increase the relevance of science learning (Ballard et al., 2017, Roche et al., 2020). However, substantial variability existed in how educational outcomes were conceptualised and evaluated. Few studies used validated educational frameworks, longitudinal approaches or systematic assessment tools, and many described outcomes only briefly or anecdotally. Strengthening collaboration between citizen science practitioners, education researchers and teachers may therefore support more rigorous evaluation and a clearer understanding of the educational impacts of school-based citizen science over time. This is particularly important given the practical and methodological challenges of conducting research in school settings, including ethics requirements, competing curriculum priorities, limited teacher time and capacity, and the complexities of longitudinal data collection (Braz Sousa et al., 2024, Müller et al., 2025).

Importantly, not all school-based citizen science studies were primarily designed to evaluate student learning. Many focused on generating scientific data, testing monitoring approaches or implementing projects, which may partly explain the limited reporting of educational outcomes in the reviewed literature. In many cases, schools functioned primarily as sites for data collection rather than as contexts for investigating pedagogy or student learning.

Typology of Projects

Contributory, Collaborative and Co-Created Citizen Science

The predominance of contributory projects identified in this review reflects broader trends across citizen science literature internationally. Previous studies consistently report that citizen science initiatives are heavily concentrated within Ecology, Environmental Sciences and Biodiversity Monitoring, with most projects primarily positioning participants as contributors to scientist-led data collection efforts (Hecker et al., 2018, Lukyanenko et al., 2020, Golumbic, 2024). This pattern may partly reflect the practical demands of generating large-scale, standardised and scientifically reliable datasets, which often rely on structured protocols and researcher-led methodologies (Lukyanenko et al., 2020). Within school settings, these challenges may be further shaped by curriculum requirements, limited classroom time and varying levels of teacher confidence or scientific expertise. Nevertheless, the collaborative and co-created projects identified in this review demonstrate important opportunities to strengthen student agency, interdisciplinary learning and more

participatory approaches to scientific knowledge production (Weingart and Meyer, 2021, Golumbic, 2024).

Learning Areas Represented in School-Based Citizen Science Projects

Natural World

Biology emerged as the most-represented area of school-based citizen science, reflecting the strong emphasis on biodiversity monitoring, species identification, and ecological investigations in educational settings. However, fewer biology-focused examples were identified in schools than might be expected given the broader dominance of biological and ecological citizen science in community contexts (Follett and Strezov, 2015, Davis et al., 2023). Contrary to expectations, ornithology was less common than microbiology within school settings, where projects frequently involved analysing microbes from everyday environments, such as testing bacterial growth on classroom surfaces, comparing microbes collected from students' hands, or investigating water quality through microbial sampling (van Tonder et al., 2023, Gil-Serna et al., 2025, Cornwell et al., 2024). These activities provided authentic scientific experiences while connecting students to real-world questions.

Earth and Environmental Science was the second most represented area, with projects such as air quality monitoring and coastal litter surveys widely implemented, likely due to their accessibility and direct relevance to students' local environments. These activities commonly rely on simple, safe and readily available equipment, making them feasible across schools with varying levels of resourcing (Kelemen-Finan et al., 2018).

Chemistry, Physics and Technology

Physics and technology projects represented a relatively small proportion of the studies identified, with both disciplines showcasing advanced scientific and computational applications where they were featured. Physics projects in Europe, such as stellar object detection or radiation studies, exposed students to sophisticated scientific inquiry (Gustavsson et al., 2019, Lantz et al., 2019, D'Agostino et al., 2020, Edwards et al., 2021). Technology projects included initiatives centred on digital tools and programming platforms, such as Arduino and air:bit (Fjukstad et al., 2018, Na et al., 2022). Nonetheless, interdisciplinary examples such as “Beat the Pathologists” (UK) illustrated how citizen science can integrate computing, engineering and health sciences while engaging students in real-world problem solving (Lu et al., 2022). These findings suggest significant room to expand technology-oriented citizen science in schools, particularly using accessible digital tools and emerging technologies.

Chemistry was notably underrepresented, with only 4% of projects falling within this discipline, and all in secondary schools. The absence of primary-level chemistry projects suggests opportunities to introduce early exploratory experiences to demystify the subject and support student interest. Projects involving physicochemical measurements and pollution analyses demonstrate how citizen science can make chemistry more tangible and relevant, as participants analyse environmental data from their local areas and see the direct applicability of chemistry within their own communities. This underrepresentation may also reflect the limited availability and visibility of chemistry-focused citizen science projects more broadly, as previous curriculum mapping efforts have similarly identified difficulties locating suitable examples for school implementation (Learning By Doing, 2021).

Humanities and Health

Health and Physical Education projects (n = 24) were limited and largely concentrated in North America and Europe. These projects addressed a wide range of topics including lifestyle behaviours, infectious diseases, mental health and environmental health, demonstrating the potential of citizen science to connect students with community wellbeing. However, the scarcity of such projects indicates a missed opportunity to leverage citizen science in public health education.

Humanities and Social Sciences projects were also relatively uncommon, with 23 projects identified across Civics and Citizenship, Geography, History, Economics and Business, and multidisciplinary HASS initiatives. The interdisciplinary MALIA project exemplifies how citizen science can foster learning across Geology, Biology, Chemistry and Digital Technologies while empowering students to propose evidence-based environmental solutions (Gravina et al., 2019). Expanding humanities-oriented citizen science could help students explore the social dimensions of science, policy and civic action or indeed promote interest in participatory research in non-science disciplines.

Multidisciplinary Potential

Citizen science holds considerable promise as a multidisciplinary pedagogical approach that can strengthen connections across learning areas. Projects that integrate science with English, Mathematics, the Arts or Technologies can support communication, numeracy, creativity and digital literacy in authentic and interconnected ways. For example, students can develop numeracy skills by quantifying beach debris during coastal surveys and simultaneously strengthen literacy skills by writing reports that communicate their findings to school or community audiences (Duckett and Repaci, 2015, Giovacchini et al., 2018, Wichmann et al., 2022, Merlino et al., 2023c). Students can also build digital competencies through data entry, map comparison or the use of online platforms to explore spatial patterns in their observations. Despite this potential, representation of school-

based citizen science across disciplines remains markedly uneven and there are relatively few examples of projects that explicitly span multiple disciplines

Most of the school-based citizen science projects published to date focus on Ecology, Biology and Environmental Science, with far fewer examples in Chemistry, Physics, Digital Technologies, Public Health or the Humanities. This imbalance may partly reflect the broader availability and visibility of citizen science initiatives within environmental fields, where participatory approaches are already well established. Expanding citizen science into a wider range of disciplines therefore requires not only increased adoption in schools, but also the development of new projects intentionally designed for diverse curriculum areas and educational contexts. Schools and educational settings have the potential to play an important role in this process by supporting the co-creation and implementation of projects that align with curriculum needs from the outset and make citizen science more accessible across disciplines (Golumbic, 2025). Broadening multidisciplinary applications would diversify learning opportunities while reflecting the wide range of scientific and societal questions that citizen science can address within school contexts.

Engaging First Nations Peoples and Remote School Communities

Across the global literature, collaboration with First Nations communities and the integration of Indigenous Knowledges remain strikingly scarce in school-based citizen science. This absence represents a critical gap in the field and underscores an urgent need to strengthen inclusion and social justice by more fully engaging with the deep ecological knowledge and lived experience of Indigenous communities (Ens et al., 2015). Similarly, remote and regional schools are underrepresented in published research, despite the unique perspectives and biodiversity contexts these communities can offer. Citizen science offers a valuable opportunity to recognise and amplify Indigenous Knowledges, local expertise and place-based perspectives within science education; however, this potential remains underutilised in both school-based and broader citizen science literature. The few studies that do highlight these collaborations demonstrate the transformative potential of such work, showing strong scientific contributions alongside meaningful cultural, educational and community outcomes (Webber et al., 2021, Dampney et al., 2022, Walker et al., 2023, Sharp et al., 2024, Turner-jones et al., 2024, Riley et al., 2025). The overall scarcity of studies suggests systemic barriers related to funding, digital access, research partnerships and publication pathways. Addressing these gaps will require intentional efforts to build equitable collaborations, support teacher capacity in remote regions and ensure that Indigenous Knowledges are valued, safeguarded and appropriately embedded within citizen science programs.

Limitations

This review has several limitations. Only peer-reviewed papers published in English were included, which likely contributed to the underrepresentation of studies from countries where other languages predominate. The reliance on two major databases may also have excluded relevant grey literature, unpublished evaluations, or locally circulated educational resources. Additionally, reporting practices varied widely across studies, particularly regarding learning outcomes, participation models and theoretical frameworks. Future reviews could incorporate multilingual searches, grey literature and regional databases to capture a more comprehensive and inclusive picture of global school-based citizen science.

Future Outlook

The findings of this review suggest that school-based citizen science is an expanding but uneven field, currently concentrated in ecology-focused projects and Global North contexts. The review highlights important opportunities to broaden disciplinary scope, geographic representation and understanding of educational and scientific outcomes. Although many projects report strong scientific contributions, for citizen science in schools to scale and be sustainable, the next stage of project development requires more deliberate incorporation of pedagogical frameworks, clearer curriculum alignment and more systematic reporting of learning outcomes. Strengthening the theoretical and curricular foundations of citizen science will support teachers in embedding these projects within regular classroom practice rather than viewing them as occasional extensions.

Addressing the practical challenges identified in recent studies will also be essential. Teachers consistently report limited time, insufficient access to resources, and a lack of clarity about which citizen science projects are available and how they map onto required learning outcomes (Braz Sousa et al., 2024). Future work should therefore prioritise creating well-structured, curriculum-aligned resources, improving visibility and discoverability of existing projects and developing professional learning that builds teacher confidence and capacity. These steps would mitigate common barriers and support broader and more sustainable adoption across school systems.

A further priority is the need to address geographical and social inequities in participation. The review highlights a strong concentration of studies in the Global North and a substantial underrepresentation of projects from the Global South, as well as limited engagement with First Nations communities and remote schools. Expanding collaborations with Indigenous communities and strengthening support for remote educators would enhance cultural responsiveness, recognise Indigenous Ecological Knowledge and create more equitable opportunities for students to participate in authentic scientific inquiry.

Future research should also consider more diverse methodological approaches. Few studies track long-term outcomes or involve students and teachers in co-designed evaluations, limiting understanding of how citizen science shapes scientific literacy, identity and environmental stewardship over time. Longitudinal and mixed-method designs would provide deeper insights into the educational and community impacts of participation.

Finally, the field would benefit from improved international coordination and more inclusive synthesis of evidence. Reviews incorporating grey literature and publications in languages other than English would provide a more accurate understanding of global activity in school-based citizen science. By addressing these conceptual, practical and geographic gaps, future work can position citizen science as a powerful and equitable approach for connecting young people with real world scientific practices.

Conclusions

This review demonstrates the substantial value of school-based citizen science in enriching science education, generating meaningful scientific outcomes and strengthening relationships between schools, communities and research partners. Across the included studies, students engaged in authentic scientific practices that supported inquiry-based learning, data literacy and increased confidence in working with real-world problems. Teachers also used citizen science to make curriculum content more relevant by connecting learning to local environments, issues and expertise.

At the same time, this review highlights important gaps in current practice and scholarship. Many published studies foreground scientific results while providing limited detail about pedagogical design, assessment or long-term learning benefits. Projects involving rural, regional or remote schools, and those meaningfully integrating First Nations knowledges, remain scarce even though available evidence shows that these collaborations can generate significant educational, cultural and scientific contributions. Furthermore, most initiatives focus on Ecology and Environmental Science. Other disciplines, including Public Health, Chemistry, Engineering, Astronomy and Digital Technologies, remain underrepresented despite their strong potential for productive citizen science integration.

A critical concern identified in this review is the uneven school participation. Many public schools, particularly those experiencing structural disadvantage, have limited access to the time, resources and support required to implement citizen science. Ensuring that citizen science is genuinely accessible to all schools is essential for promoting educational equity and for realising the broader

societal promise of participatory science as a pathway to inclusion and justice.

Together, these findings show that while school-based citizen science is a vibrant and expanding field, its full educational and societal potential has not yet been realised. By recognising both achievements and shortcomings, this review provides a foundation for strengthening future initiatives so that all young people, regardless of geography, background or school resourcing, can participate meaningfully in scientific discovery and develop the capabilities needed to engage with science throughout their lives.

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